

PROJECT PUBLISH: COMPLETING RESEARCH PAPERS THROUGH PUBLICATION

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ABSTRACT

This innovation project aimed at empowering teacher-researchers in the Eastern Samar Division to publish their academic work in reputable journals. Recognizing that research is not complete until it is published, this project addresses the gap between conducting research and its dissemination. The initiative provides comprehensive support through training, mentorship, and access to publishing resources, thereby enhancing the research capacity of educators. The project's objectives include equipping teacher-researchers with the skills necessary for independent research, fostering a collaborative environment thereby increasing the number of published studies. Through focusing on these goals, the project has successfully elevated the role of research within the division, resulting in a noticeable increase in the publication of high-quality research projects. The impact of the project extends beyond individual professional development; it has also contributed to their academic growth in the said division, improved teaching practices, and positively influenced student outcomes. The initiative has fostered a culture of research and continuous learning, transforming teacher-researchers into active contributors to both local and global educational knowledge. Reflecting on the project's success, it is recommended that the division continues to invest in research capacity-building to sustain and expand these achievements. Ultimately, "Project Publish" emphasizes the importance of publishing as a critical step in the research process, enabling teacher-researchers to make meaningful contributions to the broader educational landscape.

Keywords: *Publication, reputable journals, research capacity-building, teacher-researchers.*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) stays to strengthen the culture of research and evidence-based decision-making in basic education. Research can help tackle specific practice problems and give a strong reference point to guide teaching. Anent to this, DepEd Order (DO) No. 16, s.2017 titled Research Management Guidelines (RMG) was issued to launch a complete framework for managing research including the Basic Education Research Fund (BERF), and DO 14, s.2022 to establish E-Saliksik as its official portal of education research.

Meanwhile, the demanding process of research writing includes publication. Hence, research isn't completely done until it's published (Hashini et.al., 2022). Teachers had been dreaming of publishing their academic writing for all kinds of publication purposes such as research papers through the conceptualized assistance for the school innovation for quality and excellence. Teachers were only exposed to sample academic papers, then ask them to write their own but limited time to think about publication methods. This practice has shown minimal impact to academe especially those who are not into academic reading and writing for researchers to publish in the entirety of their journey in showcasing their principles and theories in their great endeavor of establishing academic or educational milestone of innovations.

Moreover, Gastel & Day (2022), there was little confusion regarding the typical one-paragraph abstracts published as part of the program or distributed along with the program at a national meeting or international congress. It was usually understood that many of the papers presented at these meetings would later be submitted for publication in primary journals. Busse & August (2020), communicating research findings is an essential step in the research process. More often, peer-reviewed journals are the forum for such communication, yet many researchers are never taught how to write a publishable scientific paper.

Explaining the basic structure of a scientific paper and describe the information that should be included in each section. So also, identifying common pit falls for each section and recommend strategies to avoid the unethical considerations or ethical inconsideration. Furthermore, advising about target journal selection and authorship (Alves, 2021; Becker, 2020). Peer reviewer guidelines from your target journal are an additional resource that can help you tailor your writing to the journal and provide additional advice about crafting an effective article (International Committee of Medical Journal Editors, 2020).

Journals vary in their approach to strengths and limitations sections: some are embedded paragraphs within the discussion section, while some mandate separate section headings. Keep in mind that every study has strengths and limitations. Candidly reporting yours helps readers to correctly interpret your research findings (Banik et. al., 2020).

Búky, Schwartz, & Einsohn (2019), general media too can aid in publicizing your newly published research, both to the public and to fellow researchers. In the catalogue made by the San Pedro College Research, Publication and Innovation Center in 2020, according to their research manual, there must be an institution who advocates collaboration and sharing of resources encouraging teachers, experts, and practitioners from other fields of specialization or disciplines in developing and conducting their research projects. In this way, they build their social and professional network for stronger collaborative activities. Warner (2021), using published papers as models, and perhaps using detailed outlines of them to help structure your own paper, that can prepare you to craft a manuscript that will be suitable for submission.

Additionally, in the article of Robens (2023) he underscored that It does not matter how important a researcher's results are, if no one knows about them, they'll have no impact. So, it is essential for researchers to communicate their results with others to advance their field. Regardless of the publishing mechanism, the primary goal is to disseminate new results, discuss that information, and ultimately generate knowledge.

It is high time for the country's educational landscape to upscale teachers-researchers' academic works. Correspondingly, in the 21st century teaching process, it is imperative that teachers are given the platform to apply their skills in research to meaningful undertaking. As such, the proponent took the challenge. Project Publish for the publication technique and method made by the innovator - researcher, as an offshoot of a bigger innovative practice through assistance in research publications as research publication undergoes a certain extent of reviews and evaluation as to the veracity on the content of the paper to be published.

There is a need to realize that that even in their younger years in formal education, teachers can already start contributing to community development by means of research publishing endeavors. Hence, researchers make significant contributions to the advancement of essential information and knowledge production. Research findings might make a great impact to the world. Accomplishments have the potential to save lives, alter our perceptions of the world, and improve living standards.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this process innovation include the following:

1. To equip teacher-researchers with the necessary skills and knowledge to independently conduct high-quality research and successfully navigate the publication process.
2. To facilitate peer review and feedback, ensuring the academic rigor and quality of submissions.
3. To increase the number of research studies successfully published in reputable journals by providing targeted support and resources to teacher-researchers.
4. To use the publication process as a platform for professional growth, enabling teacher-researchers to gain recognition and build their academic profiles.

5. To develop the overall research capacity within the Eastern Samar Division by creating a sustainable system of mentorship and support to teacher-researchers.
6. To cultivate a culture of research and continuous learning among teachers, encouraging them to view research as an integral part of their professional practice.
7. To guide teacher-researchers in producing research that is both academically rigorous and directly relevant to educational challenges in their local context.
8. To support teacher-researchers in publishing studies that contribute to innovative educational practices, thereby impacting teaching and learning within the division and beyond.

METHODOLOGY

This section consists of the key features of the innovation, including the persons involved, locale, resources used, and cost of the project. The methods for gathering information and sources of information, both primary and secondary are also herein explained.

Key Features. This type of innovation involves improving the methods and processes used in a particular setting—in this case, the process of conducting and publishing research. This innovation includes providing support and resources for research development, offering workshops or training on writing and publishing, or creating collaborative opportunities for co-authorship. This process innovation enhanced the ability of teachers to contribute to academic knowledge, which can lead to improved teaching practices and professional development.

Persons Involved. In this project, the key persons involved were research managers and teacher-researchers. Research managers play a crucial role in guiding and supporting teacher-researchers throughout the research and publication process. They provide expert advice on research methodologies, assist in refining research questions, and offer critical feedback on drafts to ensure the academic rigor of the work. Teacher-researchers, on the other hand, are the driving force behind the research initiatives. They brought their classroom experiences, insights, and innovative ideas into their studies, aiming to contribute meaningful findings to the educational community. Together, these two groups collaborated closely to transform research projects into published works that enhance both professional development and the broader academic landscape.

Locale. The locale of this project was in the Schools Division Office (SDO) Eastern Samar. This region, known for its rich cultural heritage and strong commitment to education, serves as an ideal setting for the initiative. The SDO presents a diverse range of educational contexts, making it a fertile ground for research and innovation. Through focusing on this area, the project also aimed at empowering local teacher-researchers, providing them with the necessary tools and support to publish their research findings. This not only enhance their professional growth but also contribute to the advancement

of educational practices within the division, which will also benefit students and the broader community.

Resources Used. In this project, the primary resource utilized was access to international journal publishing platforms. These platforms served as the gateway for teacher-researchers to disseminate their scholarly work on a global scale. The project made sure that the research conducted in Eastern Samar Division satisfies strict academic standards and is widely disseminated by utilizing respectable international journals. This exposure not only elevates the professional standing of the teacher-researchers but also contributes to the global body of educational knowledge. Through this resource, the project supported the publication of research that can influence educational practices both locally and internationally fostering a culture of academic excellence.

Cost of the Project. The cost of implementing this project was approximately Php 20,000.00. This budget was strategically allocated to cover various essential aspects, including resources for research development, access to international journal publishing platforms, and the organization of workshops or training sessions for teacher-researchers. The expenditure reflected the commitment to providing high-quality support and opportunities for teachers to publish their work, thereby enhancing their professional growth and contributing to academic excellence. Despite the modest budget, the project effectively maximized resources to achieve significant outcomes, making it a cost-efficient initiative with a substantial impact on the educational community in Eastern Samar Division.

Methods of Gathering Information. In this project, the method of gathering information involved a systematic collection of completed research studies, including Action Research, Innovations, Theses, and Dissertations. These finished works, produced by teacher-researchers within the Eastern Samar Division, are carefully compiled to serve as the foundation for the publication process. Once collected, these studies are submitted to peer-reviewed journals for evaluation. This rigorous review process ensures that the research meets high academic standards and contributes valuable insights to the educational field. In addition to promoting knowledge dissemination, the project fosters a culture of scholarly inquiry and ongoing professional development among educators by assisting in the submission of these studies to respected journals.

Sources of Information. In this project, the primary sources of information were the full-blown studies conducted by teacher-researchers within the Eastern Samar Division. These comprehensive research projects, encompassing Action Research, Innovations, Theses, and Dissertations, form the core content for publication. Each study reflects the unique insights and experiences of educators who are deeply engaged in addressing real-world educational challenges. The project made sure that the researches published were based on real-world, classroom-based inquiry by using these comprehensive studies, which added to the local and wider academic discourse. These sources of information were invaluable in showcasing the innovative practices and pedagogical advancements that teacher-researchers bring to the field, thereby reinforcing the project's mission to

enhance the professional development of educators and the quality of education in the region.

RESULTS

The implementation of this project has found to have a profound impact on the Eastern Samar Division's educational community. This initiative has significantly enhanced the capacity of teacher-researchers to contribute to academic knowledge by providing them with the necessary tools, resources, and support to publish their research outputs. As a result, there have been a noticeable increase in the number of research papers submitted and accepted for publication in reputable international journals. This not only raised the professional profile of the teachers involved but also positions the Eastern Samar Division as a beacon of educational innovation and excellence.

Moreover, the project has established a structured and sustainable process for research and publication, allowing for continuous improvement and the systematic sharing of best practices across the division. This structured approach has led to more rigorous and impactful research being conducted, fostering a culture of academic inquiry and professional growth among teachers.

The learners, too, have benefited from this project, as researches conducted often focused on practical classroom applications that directly enhance teaching and learning. The insights gained from published research have led to the development of new teaching strategies and educational interventions, improving student outcomes and contributing to a more dynamic and responsive educational environment.

For the personnel in the school, particularly the teacher-researchers, the project has been transformative. It has empowered them to see themselves not just as educators but as scholars capable of contributing to the broader educational discourse. This shift in identity has led to increased motivation and a sense of professional fulfilment, as teachers realize the value and impact of their work beyond the classroom.

DISCUSSION

It is clear that "PROJECT PUBLISH" has been a critical step in elevating the role of research within the Eastern Samar Division. The journey of implementing of this project has been both challenging and rewarding. This initiative has revealed the immense potential that lies within our teacher-researchers when they are given the right tools, guidance, and opportunities to share their work with the broader academic community. The success of the project reflects a growing recognition of the importance of research in

education—not just as a theoretical exercise, but as a practical tool for improving teaching and learning process.

One of the key reflections from this project was the transformation in the mindset of our educators. Teacher-researchers, who once viewed research as an overwhelming task, now see it as an integral part of their professional identity. This shift has led to a more engaged and motivated teaching force, one that is eager to contribute to the body of knowledge that shapes educational practices. However, the project also highlighted some areas for improvement. While the increase in published research is commendable, there is still a need to ensure that all teachers feel confident and capable in conducting and publishing their research. Additionally, the project has shown that a supportive and collaborative environment is crucial for sustaining this momentum. Research enthusiasts played a vital role, and their continued involvement and development will be essential for future success. To sustain and build upon these successes, it is recommended that the division continues to invest in research capacity-building initiatives. Expanding access to workshops, providing ongoing mentorship, and ensuring that resources for publication are readily available will be crucial in maintaining the momentum generated by this project.

Conclusions

The project has not only met its objectives but has also laid a strong foundation for continued academic excellence and innovation within the Eastern Samar Division. Through this initiative, teachers have become active participants in the educational community, contributing to the advancement of knowledge and the betterment of their own educational practices.

Recommendations

This innovation project may be implemented not only in Schools Division of Eastern Samar but in the entire country and even international. Hence, research is never finished if not undergo on publication. Through fostering a culture of research and collaboration, the project ensured that teacher-researchers were not just participants in education but active contributors to the body of knowledge that shapes it. Ultimately, this initiative emphasized the importance of publishing as a critical step in the research process, enabling teacher-researchers to make meaningful contributions to both their local communities and the broader educational landscape.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The proponent of this innovation complied with ethical standards in the conduct of this undertakings. Persons involved in this project obtained informed consent. Moreover, freedom to withdraw was emphasized and their anonymity was maintained. Their well-

being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this innovative project.

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